

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AT TAY NGUYEN UNIVERSITYNguyen Thi Nhu¹, Phan Thi Dai Trang¹

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SUMMARY

Digital transformation is taking place firmly and has become a vital issue for businesses as well as social organizations. Tay Nguyen University, like other universities, is expected to lead in digital transformation because it is the central place to train human resources for society. The higher education environment derives employees' knowledge, skills, and professional experience. Therefore, with the growing demand for the digital transformation, universities need to implement digital transformation not only in the field of teaching and training but also in comprehensive digital transformation, creating a digital living environment for citizens of their organizations. In this research, methods of observing and synthesizing documents were implemented to discover a suitable solution for digital transformation at Tay Nguyen university

Keywords: *Digital transformation, university, education.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation is the process of moving from a traditional model to a digital model based on new technologies (Clark, 2018) such as big data, the Internet of Things, cloud computing and technology software to change the management and administration methods, processes, working methods, and organizational culture.

Industry 4.0, digital transformation is considered the key to improve operations, increase competitiveness for businesses and organizations through the outstanding advantages which bring such as optimizing operating costs, improving quality productivity and diversifying products and services.

For education in general, and higher education in particular, digital transformation offers the opportunity to apply technology to create rapid changes in model, organization and teaching and learning methods. Traditional classes with disadvantages such as high organizational costs, limited serving space, and fixed time... will be replaced by online and virtual classes. The learning space is more diverse, instead of traditional laboratories or simulation rooms, learners can experience learning in virtual space, interact human-to-human or human-machine through VR technology simulation software.

The decision No 1282 made by Ministry of Education and Training for project “Enhancing information technology application and digital transformation in education and training in the period of 2022 - 2025, oriented to 2030” (The Ministry of Education and Training, 2022) which refers to the

determination of leaders in digital higher education model in Vietnam. This project helps universities quickly transform into new model.

In Viet Nam, estimated about 45% universities are in digital transforming, Ho Chi Minh national universities implements digital transforming and get successful at 4th of pilot stage, others can study or inherit their model (Liên, 2022).

Tay Nguyen University is training organization to supply the main human resources for the central highlands provinces and surrounding areas. Therefore, society has great expectations for human resources to experience the results of digital transformation to apply in the working process. Over the years, Tay Nguyen University has gradually implemented digitization. Departments, lecturers and staffs have been making efforts to apply information technology and digitize work contents. However, in order to reach development of digital transformation, the university needs to focus on investing more in the fields of digital transformation, such as strategy building, human resource training, equipment and infrastructure...

2. RESEARCH CONTENTS AND METHODOLOGIES**2.1. Research contents**

The study focuses on the following key issues:

Elements of digital transformation at universities in the industrial stage 4.0

Trends of digital transformation in university education.

The digital transformation model from organizations

¹Faculty of Science and Technology, Tay Nguyen University;

Corresponding author: Nguyen Thi Nhu; Tel: 0906200625; Email: ntnhu@ttn.edu.vn.

Requirements and challenges of digital transformation for university education institutions.

Digital conversion for teaching activities.

Digital transformation for scientific research activities.

Current situation and some solutions for digital transformation for Tay Nguyen University.

2.2. Research methodologies

Synthesize documents of digital transformation in universities around the world and in Vietnam, study documents on digitization and digital transformation of major universities in the world, and learn digital transformation models suitable for the educational environment in Vietnam.

Observe and learn about the application of technology in administration and teaching and

research activities at Tay Nguyen University.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Elements of digital transformation

Digital transformation is “a change in the operation ways of an organization to improve the quality of products and services by exploiting the application of technology and data” (Quân, 2021). For university education, this goal is to improve the effectiveness of administration, the quality of training, and serve the development of the country. In essence, digital transformation does not change the core values or model of an university education organization, but transforms core operations through technology and digital platforms, and seizes opportunities which are bring. In other words, digital transformation is the intersection between technology and training strategy.

Figure 1. Drivers, components and outcomes of digital transformation in university education (Grajek, 2019)

3.2. Trends of digital transformation in university education

Some digital transformation trends at major universities around the world as well as the effects that digital transformation can bring:

Expanding the target students, increase the enrollment target by combining online and face-to-face training; reduce costs but increase training quality.

Collecting and analyzing learners’ big data to find out the factors affecting learning outcomes, thereby making adjustments to policies, teaching methods, and assessment methods to improve training quality, and meet the increasing requirements of learners as well as of society.

Using direct/online connections with businesses/employees to train necessary skills and knowledge, helping learners to be able to work immediately after graduation.

Application of augmented reality to create an interactive learning environment, enhancing the learning experiences for learners.

Applying artificial intelligence to personalize the learning process, support and improve the effectiveness of teaching, management, and tutoring...

3.3. Digital transformation process

Figure 2. Digital transformation process (Noscotek, 2018)

There are five main phases that every organization or university should undergo on their journey of becoming digital

The first phase is to move from paper to digital information

Phase two is the categorisation of documents

The third phase is the process of eliminating inefficient processes

Phase four includes the cumbersome processes

The last phase is to eliminate ineffectiveness

By using these processes, organizations can plan processes more proactively and quickly respond to trends or changes in the market (Noscotek, 2018).

3.4. Requirements and challenges of digital transformation

To implement digital transformation, university needs to clearly define the requirements of digital transformation and the challenges as well as the plan to deal with them.

Table 1. Requirements and challenges of digital transformation

Requirements	Challenges
Must have an mindset to adapt fast changes and accept changes from habits to processes	Ability and readiness for the digital transformation process, understanding the meaning and core values of digital transformation by leaders, lecturers, learners and stakeholders.
Must have basic knowledge about using technology in among administrators, lecturers and learners.	The initial investment cost for digital transformation is high when compared to the initial efficiency.
Must improve technology infrastructure (network and computing systems), equipment, teaching and learning software	Limitations on transmission lines, bandwidth and software and devices to support teaching and learning.

3.5. Digital transformation of teaching activities

An important component of the digital transformation process in universities is the blended learning model. This model is learner-centered,

promoting self-study and self-research abilities in setting questions and discussion, helping learners develop necessary skills to meet the requirements of employers as well as rapidly developing

industry. However, in order to implement the mixed teaching model, it is necessary to have a massive open source material with systems of highly interactive lectures, exercises, and documents. This is a big challenge in the initial stage of digital transformation because besides the investment costs to implement, it also requires the persistence of the lecturers. To perform well the mixed training model, it is necessary to meet two requirements:

Take advantage of digital tools and platforms to provide knowledge continuously, anytime, anywhere for learners.

Provide opportunities for learners to approach the real environment through co-training with enterprises. With this approach, learners will experience new learning models: learning by practical experiences, learning by problem solving methods, learning how to integrate into the real environment...

3.6. Digital transformation for scientific research activities

Currently, scientific research activities at universities are shifting the focus to data. Implementing digital transformation in scientific research activities need to focus on building data centers and connecting platforms to form a network of domestic and international scientists to solve major problems together. Specifically following:

Built a large data center to collect and accumulate sample data and experimental data in all fields. Through jointly solving problems using shared data sets, research works will be linked together, promoting cooperation, sharing results, and co-experimentation. In addition, big data centers also provide computing ability and support for experiments on big data.

Develop a scientific advisory network: this will be a place where research proposals are publicly commented and evaluated, where businesses order researches, where research proposals are received and real funding is provided presently.

Forming start-up centers where potential research results are incubated and trading exhibitions are introduced, where startup products are introduced, where stakeholders in the ecosystem are engaged, ready for investment cooperation to invest in large-scale production.

3.7. Digital transformation at Tay Nguyen University, current situations and solutions

3.7.1. Current situations of digital transformation

at Tay Nguyen University

Basically, University has built a number of solutions for administration and management. Training management system is considered as the core system, maintaining the continuity of training activities over the years. Other departments also have solutions to support the management of each task. However, there is no overall and synchronous management system such as digital management, digital signatures, digital workflow processes, etc. Therefore, the management work is inconsistent, the data is not consistent and there are still many management stages that have to be done manually.

During the last pandemic, University quickly took up solutions and supported online teaching to help ensure the progress of the training program and teaching activities continuously, adapt and quickly access the activities of digital teaching methods. However, the implementation time is short, there is no preparation, so the teaching model applied is not reasonable; lectures and teaching materials have not been digitized; Teaching methods are not effective, mainly putting the traditional teaching model on online conferences, making the training effectiveness not high. On the other hand, learners have not been assigned the task of digital learning, have not played a central role in the learning process, and have not had enough digital learning facilities.

Human resources need to be grouped and trained during digital transformation. Very few lecturers are trained in digital teaching models and methods. Not many lecturers search, exploit and apply teaching support software. Students are also rarely assigned the task of self-study and self-research on digital platforms. The group of staffs who are experts and faculty assistants should be trained on professional tasks corresponding to their assigned job positions.

Regarding scientific research, the University has a policy to allow the establishment of scientific research groups for researchers to exchange achievements and share experiences and research results. However, the University needs a solution to manage scientific research activities and accurately evaluate the activities of researchers to support for building a data center for researchers, search and share information.

For successful digital transformation, the University should have a strategy and a long-term plan, prepare funds to build a system to digitize all lectures, train human resources, negotiate and gradually transfer management system from major

universities in the country.

3.7.2. Solutions to develop digital transformation at Tay Nguyen University

Digital transformation in education is not only improving the student experience but also focusing on enhancing the campus environment, teaching and learning methods. Therefore, digital transformation in universities is generally classified into three categories:

Transform on campus including overall and synchronous administration system.

Transform learning methods

Transform teaching methods

a. Maintain continuity and adapt to training activities

The pandemic has disrupted the traditional classroom model. All training activities must be posted online. Implementing digital transformation is to maintain continuity and adaptability of training condition. To achieve this goal, digital transformation needs to meet the following conditions:

All courses should be compiled with content that can be taught both online and offline. Course outlines and materials must be fully updated before a new course begins.

Ensure to meet the minimum requirements for transmission lines, bandwidth, and necessary equipment. Have a plan to financially support or borrow equipment for learners. Organize basic training courses for lecturers and staffs on how to operate activities in the digital environment.

Add a number of compulsory basic courses on technology in the training program to provide the minimum knowledge to help learners integrate into the digital education environment.

Establish a working group on digital transformation to define standards and criteria; choose the implementation method; formulate and promulgate rules and regulations

b. Build a team of lecturers to meet high interactive technology requirements

The teaching staffs should be equipped with skills in technology and pedagogy, including teaching methods according to new approaches, methods of operating tools, digital environment, and ways of compiling digital documents. This is a long-term strategy, which should be prepared step by step when implementing digital transformation, through the following activities

Organize training courses: teaching with

technology, teaching in mixed models, training on using digital tools and platforms

Organize the design/recompile the subjects according to the mixed teaching model, open learning models and interactive lessons, etc. Some subjects can refer to use learning materials and documents from advanced universities in the world

Promote the form of rewarding lecturers with excellent teaching achievements, forming a network of excellent lecturers so that they can guide colleagues in departments or their division.

Open training programs, send lecturers to study and experience at domestic and foreign technology units

c. Expand the audience of learners and access to technology for learners

With the availability of digital classrooms, digital documents, and open learning materials, the university's target learners will no longer be constrained by age. Anyone in anywhere can participate and receive a diploma. Limitations on campus size or geographic distance will be removed. Since then, training targets and contributions to socio-economic development have also increased.

To improve ability to access technology, learners need to have conditions to approach and interact with the digital environment in both online and offline learning. Therefore, we need:

Establish interactive technology laboratories with all necessary equipment and supporting tools. Learners can realize their ideas or projects.

Build extracurricular clubs and popularize necessary technology knowledge for new learners.

Integrate virtual, augmented and mixed realities into the learning environment. This is an effective assistant for learners to experience technology.

Reduce the distribution of traditional books/documents. Instead, provide digital learning materials and an open learning materials for learners

Open 24/7 channel to answer general questions and provide technical supports..

d. Develop applications for administration and management

The general data platforms are systems of supporting applications for administration and management. These systems include the application of digital management - digital signatures, electronic offices, statistical data for university rankings, and support reports and management tasks such as rewards and classification analysis ...

These applications need to ensure consistency and interoperability throughout the system.

4. CONCLUSION

During the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers have more or less experienced using Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Team, PowerPoint or email, web software to teach online. However, digital transformation in university education is not simply about teaching online. It is the entire technology of the teaching and learning process, the automation of business and management processes. The expansion of the subjects, capacity and scope of teaching is the improvement of the quality of training and the ability to respond industrial application...

The most important skill for learners is “learning how to learn”. We have gone from a period of lacking information to the age of digital technology explosion, from sitting over night of every week in the library to sorting search results through software tools. In that context, implementation of digital transformation is considered as an indispensable activity to respond to changes, improve management effectiveness and training quality.

There are no general model for all universities or organizations because of their characteristics. Tay Nguyen University is in the first of digital transformation, the administration should registry to beneficiary the project of The decision No 1282 made by Ministry of Education and Training.

CHUYỂN ĐỔI SỐ TẠI TRƯỜNG ĐẠI HỌC TÂY NGUYÊN

Nguyễn Thị Như², Phan Thị Đài Trang²

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TÓM TẮT

Chuyển đổi số đang diễn ra mạnh mẽ và trở thành vấn đề sống còn của các doanh nghiệp cũng như các tổ chức xã hội. Trường Đại học Tây Nguyên cũng như các trường đại học khác, là nơi được kì vọng dẫn đầu trong vấn đề chuyển đổi số vì đây là nơi đào tạo nguồn nhân lực chính cho xã hội. Các kiến thức, kỹ năng, kinh nghiệm nghề nghiệp của nhân sự đều bắt nguồn từ môi trường giáo dục đại học. Vì vậy, với yêu cầu ngày càng cao về chuyển đổi số của xã hội, trường đại học cần thực hiện chuyển đổi số không chỉ trong lĩnh vực giảng dạy, đào tạo mà cần chuyển đổi số toàn diện, tạo ra môi trường sống số cho công dân của tổ chức mình. Trong nghiên cứu này, các phương thức quan sát và tổng hợp tài liệu được sử dụng để đề xuất giải pháp chuyển đổi số cho trường Đại học Tây Nguyên.

Từ khóa: Chuyển đổi số, trường đại học, giáo dục.

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²Giảng viên Khoa Khoa học Tự nhiên và Công nghệ, Trường Đại học Tây Nguyên;
Tác giả liên hệ: Nguyễn Thị Như; ĐT: 0906200625; Email: ntnhu@ttn.edu.vn.

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